

The Level Of Parents' Satisfaction Towards The Services Provided To Their Children With Speech And Language Disorder In The City Of Almadinaalmunawara

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 28, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Parents' Satisfaction, Special Educational Services, Children, Speech Disorders, Language Disorders</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4640627</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the level of parents' satisfaction regarding the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in AlmadinaAlmunawara city. The study sample consisted of (124) parents of children with speech & language disorders and through the descriptive approach and questionnaire application. The results showed that the parents' level of satisfaction towards the services provided to their children was high. The study results did not reveal any statistically significant differences in the level of satisfaction with the services provided due to the difference in sex, age, and monthly income; revealed the existence of statistically significant differences at (0.05) among study sample who have a bachelor's degree, and an intermediate qualification or less, in favor of those with an intermediate qualification or less in two dimensions (educational support services, family support services). It was found that there are statistically significant differences at (0.05) due to the child age variable between ages (less than 6) and (9 to 12) and in favor of age (less than 6). There are statistically significant differences at (0.05) due to the child's age variable between age (9 -12) and (above 12) in favor of age (above 12).</i></p>

Introduction

The field of speech and language disorders is one of the areas that has received great attention in recent times in the Arab world in general - and within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in particular, this concern is due to reducing the negative effects that speech and language disorders have on children (Al-Zoghbi, 2019). It can affect the child's social relations and his interaction with others in the surrounding environment, and it also affects the academic level, as well as his career, and it may lead to some psychological problems such as frustration, confusion, low self-concept, and self-denial (Metwally, 2015).

There is no doubt that most children with disabilities suffer from speech and language disorders more than ordinary children. In addition to what they have a disability and their problems, speech and language disorders are often a common denominator among most groups, such as the mental disability category, the learning difficulties category, cerebral palsy cases, the hearing impaired, and the children with behavioral disorders and an autism spectrum disorder. Accordingly, there is an urgent need for concerted efforts to provide services and programs and to follow early measures aimed at improving their communication skills and increasing their linguistic competence and verbal fluency (Siddiq, 2015), the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is considered one of the most prominent Arab societies that have made great and advanced achievements in the field of services provided to children with disabilities. It has issued regulations, most notably the Disabled Welfare System issued under No. (M / 37) dated 06/04/2000). Through which the state guarantees the rights of persons with disabilities in prevention, care, and rehabilitation services, and encourages institutions and individuals to contribute to charitable work in the field of disability, among these services, as stated in the system, which is provided to this category through the competent authorities in the health fields, the educational fields, the training and rehabilitation fields, the social fields, the cultural and sports fields, the complementary services fields, and the media fields.

The Ministry of Education also approved the organizational rules for governmental and private education institutes and programs by Ministerial Resolution No. 27/1647 dated 27/06/2001 accepting all children with disabilities who can learn, where educational and rehabilitative services were provided to groups that were not previously covered, such as children with speech and language disorders (Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2015).

Before that, the Ministry of Education established in the year 1419 AH / 1999AD a special department for the category of people with speech and language disorders called "the Department of Communication and Hearing Disorders," and it is one of the current administrations established to educate, teach and provide support services for people with speech and language disorders at the level of the Kingdom. The number of speech

training rooms has reached more than (148) rooms in special education institutes and programs that serve all disabilities, in line with the Ministry's directives to expand the department of educational and rehabilitation services (Ministry of Education, 2020).

So that the educational process in the institutions and programs of special education takes its right course, and to continuously improve the level of services provided to this category, parents of children must participate in this process, as they are one of the most important and basic parties in meeting the educational, and rehabilitation needs of their children in various stages (Al-Bastami, Al-Qaryouti, & Fatiha, 2017). This is what the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's vision (2030) sought to achieve, which included in its first axis strengthening the role of the family and providing it with the necessary success factors to enable it to take care of its children and develop their talents and capabilities. Accordingly, it included the launch of the "Irtiqa" program, which aims to give the family a greater role in involving it in the educational process. It stipulated the following: The "Irtiqa" program, to be launched, will include a set of performance indicators that measure the extent to which schools involve parents in the process of educating their children ... We will establish parental councils through which they present their suggestions and discuss issues affecting their children's education. And we support this by providing training programs for teachers and qualifying them to achieve effective communication with parents and to raise awareness of the importance of their participation" (Vision 2030-2017).

From this standpoint, Al-Zoghbi (2018) affirms that the issue of parents' participation and their satisfaction with the services provided to their children is among the most prominent issues and the essential considerations in the field of special education, parents are considered concerned in playing an essential role in defending the rights of their children. The role of fathers has expanded, their responsibilities increased, and they have realized their rights that have been clarified by legislation and laws during the previous decade. Among the most prominent is the Individual with Disabilities Educational Improvement Act [IDEA], 1990, which provides for the strengthening and affirmation of parental rights.

According to the law, parents have the right to review the child's records and to be part of the team that develops the individual educational program for the child, and by reviewing the law in 1997, it requires the participation of parents in the evaluation process and making decisions related to eligibility to receive special education services.

Templeman (2019) also indicated in his study that parents' satisfaction with services contributes to achieving positive results for their children, whereas analyzing the positive and negative experiences from the parent's perspective helps to know the changes that can be made in direct service provision to increase parents' satisfaction with the services, hence, children's outcomes in treatment can be improved, and studies such as this can be conducted to determine the best way to effect positive changes at the institutional level. The American Society for Hearing, Speech and Language (ASHA, 1991) stated that parents' satisfaction with services provided to their children with speech and language disorders could be considered a desirable outcome and that there is no point in arguing about the health of the child's and parent's satisfaction as a measure of quality. Moreover, customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction is an indicator of his other behaviors. Such as selection of practitioners or programs, disengagement, use of services, and complaints. Parent feedback is critical to the quality assurance process as it helps service providers identify potential areas for improvement, such as specific care quality issues, institution procedures, and is useful in program planning and evaluation. Hence, the importance of parents' role and ensuring their satisfaction with the services provided to their children should not be underestimated, as effective elements to ensure that schools and centers assume their responsibilities and as necessary elements to evaluate the quality and effectiveness of services.

A study conducted by Ruggero, McCabe, Ballard, & Munro, (2012) aimed to determine parents' satisfaction with providing speech disorders services and their suggestions for improving them. The study was based on the descriptive approach. The sample consisted of (154) parents with (192) children with speech and language disorders in Australia. The study used a questionnaire tool; the results revealed that (60%) of the parents were satisfied or satisfied with their experiences, while (27%) were dissatisfied. And Dougherty's study (2015) aimed to assess the satisfaction of parents of children enrolled in a special education program and explore the factors that affect parents' satisfaction with the individual educational plan's mechanism. The study sample consisted of (123) parents; the study used the questionnaire tool. It included demographic questions related to the parent and the child, and (23) items for the variable of parents' knowledge and satisfaction with the individual educational plan and asking them to submit open comments about special education services.

The results showed that, in general, parents were satisfied with the services provided to their children. And there were no statistically significant differences in the variable of the parent's gender, level of education, and the child's disability. Simultaneously, an important positive relationship was found between parents' knowledge of special education and their satisfaction with the individual educational plan. And Baothman's study (2016) aimed to identify the level of parents' satisfaction with the early intervention services provided to their children with intellectual disability and its relationship to some variables. The study sample consisted of (202) parents distributed among (30) early intervention centers in Jeddah and Makkah's governorates. The study used the questionnaire tool and relied on the descriptive approach. The results showed no significant differences

in the variables of the parents' type and age, his monthly income, the gender and age of the child, and the duration of his enrollment in the center. There are statistically significant differences between the sample members who have a bachelor's degree or higher and those who have an intermediate qualification or less, in favor of the sample with an intermediate qualification.

Nordstrom (2017) also conducted a study to measure parents' satisfaction and the perception of the quality of the early intervention program for their children. The study included (100) parents, the tool was the questionnaire, and it consisted of (12) elements to measure parents' satisfaction and used Likert scale (very satisfied, satisfied, dissatisfied, very dissatisfied), as well as answering four open-ended questions. The results showed that most of the parents are very satisfied with the early intervention program for their children, and there were no statistically significant differences in the variable of the parent's age, educational level, and child's age. Although the differences were not statistically significant, the satisfaction averages were slightly higher for younger parents and parents with a college education than those in the older age group (31-40) and with a high school diploma.

Alotaibi (2017) also conducted a study to measure parents' satisfaction with special education services by identifying differences in satisfaction across rural or urban living conditions in northwestern Ohio in the United States. The study sample consisted of 114 parents; the tool was a questionnaire consisting of questions about parents' satisfaction using a Likert inverse scale of (4) points (1 = very satisfied, 4 = completely dissatisfied); the questionnaire also included demographic information representing the independent variables. The results showed that parents are very satisfied with the special education programs for their children. And there were no statistically significant differences in the educational level variable of the parents.

(Slade, Eisenhower, Carter, & Blacher, 2018) conducted a study aimed at finding out the satisfaction of parents of children with autism about individual educational programs for elementary grades in the Boston-Massachusetts and Southern California area in the United States, the study sample was (142) parents. The tool was a questionnaire, a semi-structured interview; the results showed that (62%) of the parents are dissatisfied with at least one aspect of the individual educational programs, while (38%) of them were satisfied with all aspects of the program. The satisfaction variables were not related to any demographic factors, including the child's gender, age, parent's type, educational level, and the number of special education services received.

The study of Al-Balawi (2019) also aimed to determine the degree of satisfaction of parents and scholars with the support services provided to students with hearing impairment in Qurayyat; the study was based on the descriptive approach. The study sample consisted of (54) male and female teachers for students with hearing impairment and their parents, who numbered (94) parents. The tool used in the study was a questionnaire. The results showed that the degree of satisfaction of parents and teachers was moderate. And there are no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic averages of parents according to the gender variable, the educational level, and the parent's economic level over the entire tool. While there are statistically significant differences in parents' satisfaction with the two dimensions of psychological counseling services and occupational therapy services, depending on the economic level variable, and in favor of the economic level, less than (5000) riyals.

Templeman (2019) conducted a study to measure parental satisfaction with partnerships and professional family services for children with autism spectrum disorders. The study relied on the descriptive approach, and the sample consisted of (171) parents, the tool used was the questionnaire. It included demographic variables (parents' age, child's age, economic status of the family, access to insurance), the results indicated that parents' evaluations of a child's functional behaviors were negatively related to their satisfaction with the child and family-centered aspects of the services. Additionally, there was a negative correlation between child age and parental satisfaction via professional partnerships. Parents reported that they had negative experiences when they felt ignored by service providers or realized that their provider was incompetent or had difficulty getting appointments.

Finally, the study of Al-Najem (2019) aimed at identifying parents' satisfaction with the special education services provided to their children with attention deficit and hyperactivity programs in government primary schools (boys/girls) at the level of the Kingdom's regions, Riyadh, Jeddah, Dammam, Hail, and Asir. The study used a questionnaire tool, and the sample consisted of (207) parents. The results showed that parents are satisfied with the services and that there are no statistically significant differences according to the type of parents variable, educational qualification, and monthly income. In contrast, there are statistically significant differences between the category of educational qualification diploma and another category of academic qualification (primary, intermediate, secondary) in favor of those with low educational qualifications (primary, intermediate, secondary).

The Study Problem

Interest has recently increased in the nature and level of educational services and programs provided to children with disabilities in general, as a result of the direct interest of researchers, specialists, and parents, through the laws and legislations that have come to oblige these societies to provide appropriate educational and

social services to these individuals, to bring them to the maximum of their capabilities. And then achieve a state of satisfaction for both children themselves and their parents, who can comprehensively realize the effects of education on their children. They also play an essential role in their children's lives, as they are partners in the preparation and implementation of individual educational programs. Therefore, it is necessary to study and evaluate the services provided to their children from their perspective and to know their level of satisfaction with them to bridge the gap between the theoretical aspects and the actual practices applied. The feeling and desire to study parents' satisfaction with the services provided to children with speech and language disorders have also emerged through the researchers' experience of working as the speech and language specialists in the field reality of special education institutions and programs. They noted the importance of the role of parents and their participation in implementing the individual educational plan as one of the members of the work team, just as the evaluation of any of the services must be through a question and knowing the extent of the satisfaction of the beneficiaries of these services. Therefore, the two researchers believe that it is necessary to measure the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorder, to know the obstacles that prevent the provision of those services as required, and to know the strengths and weaknesses of these services to develop and improve them.

The Study Objectives

- - Know the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah.
- - Determine the differences in the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al Madinah Al Munawarah according to the parent's variables: gender (male/female), age, educational level, and monthly income.
- - Determine the differences in the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah according to the child-specific variables: gender (male/female), age.
- - Build a tool to measure parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders.

The Questions of the Study

The problem of the study revolves around its attempt to answer the main question:

What is the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech disorders?

What is the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Almadinah Almunawarah?

The main question is divided into the following sub-questions:

- The first question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah due to the variables of the parent: gender (male/female), age, educational level, monthly income?
- The second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah due to the variables about the child: gender (male/female), age?

The Importance of the Study

This study gains its importance from the importance of parents' supportive role, which can contribute effectively to the success of their children's programs as they are the first to observe the level of development of their children and the level of services provided to them. Recent trends confirm that parents have a right to effective and fruitful participation within a professional relationship framework with specialists who deal with the child (Al-Zoghbi, 2018).

Theoretical importance

According to the researchers' knowledge, the scarcity of Arab scientific research is concerned with measuring parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders. Therefore, it is hoped that this study will enrich the scientific literature related to special education services and the field of speech and language disorders.

Practical Importance

- Shed light on children's services with speech and language disorders in special education institutions and programs.

- The results of this study can help decision-makers, officials, and specialists identify the strengths and weaknesses of these services to develop and improve them.
- This study will provide scientific recommendations and proposals that help meet the needs of children with speech and language disorders and meet the requirements of their parents in the desired manner that satisfies the beneficiaries.

Terminology of study

Parents' satisfaction: It is the psychological feeling of contentment, satisfaction, and happiness for parents to fulfill their personal and psychological desires and needs. (2000).

It is defined procedurally in this study: as the total degree, which represents the response of parents or mothers or whoever bears the child's legal responsibility (such as older brothers and first-degree relatives) to the study tool.

Speech and language disorder: The American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA), 1993 defines speech and language disorders: They are impaired in the ability to receive, send, process, and understand oral and non-verbal concepts or systems and graphic symbols, and its severity ranges from mild to deep, and they may be developmental or acquired, and children may suffer from one or more of these disorders. These disorders can also lead to a primary disability or may be secondary to other disabilities.

And procedurally defined in this study: As problems that appear in the pronunciation of sounds, or in the language, whether receptive or expressive language or language delay, or fluency disturbances, and those who have communication disorders, or the hearing impaired, and cochlear implants who need hearing rehabilitation or lip-reading training, and it may be associated with other disabilities.

Services: It is one of the educational and social services provided by educational and educational institutions for children diagnosed with one or more disabilities, provided that those disabilities lead to negative effects on the child's ability to acquire the skills expected of their age group (Jarrar and Qaraish, 2012).

And it is procedurally defined in this study: As the services provided to children with speech and language disorders from diagnosis, evaluation, treatment, and support services.

Study limits and determinants

The study sample represents a group of parents of children with speech and language disorders in private and governmental special education institutions and programs in Madina El Monawara in Saudi Arabia for the year 1441/1442 AH.

Study Procedures and Methodology

The Study Methodology

The current study used the descriptive survey approach, which aims to collect data and facts about existing events, phenomena, and practices that are available for study and measurement as it is, with an attempt to adequately explain these facts without the researcher's intervention in their course (Al-Dulaimi and Saleh, 2014).

The Study Population and Sample

The study population consisted of all parents of children with speech and language disorders in private and governmental special education institutions and programs in Madina El Monawara for the academic year (1441-1442 AH). The study sample amounted to (124) parents of children with speech and language disorders in private and governmental special education institutions and programs in Medina, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Those who were selected by the available random method, and the characteristics of the sample members were distributed according to the variables of the study, including frequencies and percentages, as follows:

1. Characteristics of the individuals of the study sample of the parent

Table 1: the characteristics of the study sample individuals of the parent

variable	Levels	Repetition	percentage
Gender	Males	23	18.5%
	Females	101	81.5%
Age	Less than 30 years old	23	18.5%
	From 31-35 years old	30	24.2%
	From 36- 40 years old	33	26.6%
	Over 41 years old	38	30.6%
Academic	Intermediate and less	31	25%

qualification	Secondary	34	27.4%
	Bachelor	48	38.7%
	Postgraduate	11	8.9%
Monthly income	Less than 5000 riyals	53	42.7%
	From 10,000-5000 riyals	51	41.1%
	More than 10,000 riyals	20	16.1
Total		124	100%

Table 2: the characteristics of the child's study sample

variable	Levels	Repetition	percentage
Gender	Males	50	40.3
	Females	74	59.7
Age	Less than six years old	30	24.2
	6 to less than nine years old	42	33.9
	From 9-12 years old	21	16.9
	Over 12 years old	31	25

Study tool: The two researchers designed a questionnaire that consisted of two parts: the first section: It includes information that expresses the characteristics of the members of the study sample, according to the demographic and personal variables of the study sample (guardian of the child, the child) in terms of (Gender of Parent, age of the parent, educational level of the parent, monthly income) as for the child-specific variables, they include (the child's gender, the child's age). And the second section: Includes (42) paragraphs divided into four dimensions (diagnostic and evaluation services, speech and language training services, educational support services, family support services).

The Validity of the Study Tool

It was presented in its initial form on ((9) arbitrators, to benefit from their observations and experiences to judge the tool, in light of their directives, all the expressions that gained agreement between the arbitrators (80% or more) were retained as belonging to the fields, and by amending the arbitrators' proposals, it was ensured that the veracity of the arbitrators was verified. Thus, the questionnaire has the arbitrators' validity in its final form and consists of (60) paragraphs.

The Reliability of the Study Tool

The reliability coefficient was extracted according to the Cronbach Alpha equation for internal consistency, and for each dimension of the questionnaire and the questionnaire as a whole after applying the questionnaire to an exploratory sample of (30) individuals from the study population outside its sample, and Table (9) shows the results of that:

Table 3: Reliability coefficients for the questionnaire and questionnaire dimensions as a whole

Fields of the study tool	reliability coefficient "Cronbach alpha."
Diagnostic and evaluation services	0.957
Speech and language training services	0.965
Supportive educational services	0.946
Family support services	0.961
Total reliability	0.985

The Study Procedures

The study procedures came as follows:

1. Review previous educational literature related to parents' satisfaction.
2. Build the study tool and verifying its validity and reliability to serve the purpose of the current study.
3. Determine the study sample, which numbered 124 parents, and apply the tool to them.

4. Conduct the appropriate statistical treatment, and extracting, presenting, and discussing the results.

The Study Results and Discussion

The main question: What is the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madina Almunawara?

To answer this question, the weighted arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina were calculated in the following dimensions: (Diagnostic and evaluation services, speech, and language training services, educational support services, family support services). Table (4) shows their order in descending order according to the weighted arithmetic averages.

Table 4: Means and standard deviations of the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madina Almunawara, in descending order

N	Dimensions	Mean	Standard deviation	Arrangement	Level of satisfaction
1	Diagnostic and evaluation services	3.64	0.81	1	High
2	Speech and language training services	3.64	0.93	2	High
3	Supportive educational services	3.58	0.86	3	High
4	Family support services	3.50	0.96	4	High
	Services provided as a whole	3.59	0.81	High	

It is evident from Table (4) that the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Al-Madina Almunawara was high, where the general average was (3.59). With a standard deviation of (0.81), and for all instrument dimensions, this is in line with the endeavors and policies of special education institutions and programs in their severe and relentless endeavor towards activating the services provided to children with speech and language disorders and achieving their desired goals of caring for this group, developing their abilities, treating them and meeting their needs and the needs of their parents. The results of this study are consistent with the study of Ruggero et al. (2012), Daugherty (2015), Baothman (2016), Alotaibi (2017), Nordstrom (2017), Najm (2019), and the results which indicated a high level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children. On the other hand, this result differs with the study of Dababneh (2016) and Al-Balwi (2019), which showed that the degree of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children was average on the overall score, and the study of Slade et al. (2018), which showed that (62%) of the parents are somewhat dissatisfied with at least one aspect of the individual educational programs, while (38%) of the parents were satisfied with the four aspects of the program.

Concerning arranging the dimensions of the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, the dimension "Diagnostic and evaluation services" came in first place, reaching an average of (3.64) with a standard deviation (0.81), then the dimension "speech and language training services" came in second place with an arithmetic mean of (3.64) with a standard deviation (0.93). Then, in the third place, it was followed by the "educational support services" dimension with a mean (3.58) with a standard deviation (0.86), and in the fourth and final place, the dimension "family support services" with an arithmetic mean of (3.50) with a standard deviation (0.96). And we find that the high parents' satisfaction has focused on the two dimensions of diagnostic and evaluation services and speech and language training services, and this may be due to the competence of its providers, which ensures the provision of effective services, the effects of which appear through the child's linguistic and verbal progress and parents' satisfaction with them. While the family support dimension obtained the lowest average satisfaction from parents compared to the other mean dimensions, and this can be explained by the lack of interest on the part of institutions to educate parents, support and guide them in dealing with their children and help them in how to develop their language and correct their pronunciation, as well as their lack of awareness of their rights and the rights of their children. And to find out in detail the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, it was taken according to the questionnaire's dimensions. And as follows:

The first dimension: Diagnostic and evaluation services

Table 5: Means and standard deviations for parents' satisfaction with the diagnostic and evaluation services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah, in descending order

N	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Level of satisfaction
15	The multidisciplinary team maintains the confidentiality of my child's evaluation information.	3.98	0.86	1	High

8	I have been discussed my child's strengths and weaknesses.	3.79	1.14	2	High
10	My child received the services as soon as the registration procedures for the institution were completed.	3.78	1.08	3	High
6	All my child's communication skills were assessed (Perceptual, Receptive, Expressive, Pronunciation, and Sound)	3.76	1.02	4	High
16	The evaluation took enough time to diagnose my child's condition.	3.72	1.06	5	High
11	The assessment and diagnosis process was carried out by qualified staff specializing in language and communication disorders.	3.71	0.99	6	High
7	It included evaluating my child's condition from all aspects, such as examining speech organs and audio-visual discrimination.	3.70	1.07	7	High
9	After the diagnostic process was completed, an interview was conducted with the parent to explain the report.	3.69	1.12	8	High
17	The evaluation process for my child was conducted in an organized and accurate manner.	3.69	1.13	9	High
13	The diagnosis and evaluation process was carried out according to flexible controls and deadlines.	3.66	1.03	10	High
1	I did a social case study for my child and family.	3.65	1.05	11	High
5	The diagnosis was made, taking into account the difference in the dialect.	3.60	1.02	12	High
3	The foundation keeps an eye on my child's medical and health checks.	3.56	1.08	13	High
14	There was cooperation between the speech therapist and the diagnostic team to observe, record the results, write recommendations, and define the services my child needs.	3.53	1.14	14	High
12	I participated in assessment and diagnosis as a member of the individualized education program team.	3.48	0.86	15	High
2	The diagnostic process included reports, scans, and x-rays related to my child, and a report is made on them.	3.47	1.16	16	High
4	Different types of diagnostic tests are available for different conditions with speech and language disorders.	3.42	1.16	17	High
18	The evaluation results were used in designing an individualized educational program for my child.	3.41	1.17	18	High
Diagnostic and evaluation services		3.64	0.81		High

It is evident from Table (5) that the level of parents' satisfaction with the diagnostic and evaluation services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina was high, with a mean of (3.64). It is also noticed that the value of the standard deviation of the general mean is equal to (0.81), and the arithmetic averages ranged between (3.41-3.98), paragraph (15) states, "The multidisciplinary team shall maintain the confidentiality of the information regarding the evaluation of my child." In the first place, with a mean of (3.98). And this can be explained by the fact that society's nature tends to be conservative and private, which prompts parents to pay attention to this aspect. While paragraph (18) was states, "The evaluation results were used in the design of the individual educational program for my child." In the last place, with an arithmetic mean of (3.41). And this can be explained by the lack of standardized tests for speech and language disorders in the Saudi environment and the lack of standardized tests from competent authorities such as the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Social Development to apply it to children by practitioners. Indeed, most speech and language specialists do personal diligence in designing unregulated evaluation forms. It may be disproportionate to the situation or type of disorder, in addition to the lack of training programs to qualify speech and language specialists in how to diagnose and evaluate various types of speech and language disorders and how to build a plan and design an individual educational program for the child based on the evaluation results they reach.

The second dimension: Speech and language training services

Table 6: Means and standard deviations for parents' satisfaction with the speech and language training services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, arranged in descending order

N	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Level of satisfaction
9	My baby care staff addresses me in an easy-to-understand language.	3.88	1.10	1	High
4	I participated in setting the goals of the individual educational program.	3.83	1.15	2	High
3	My child receives speech sessions by qualified staff specializing in language and communication disorders.	3.81	1.06	3	High
8	I can contact the speech therapist or the team caring for my child whenever I need it and by whatever means is right for me.	3.78	1.23	4	High
14	The speech therapist uses reinforcement techniques appropriate and friendly to my child to increase their motivation in the program.	3.73	1.01	5	High
2	The institution informs me of the session schedule or cancellation of the session's insufficient time.	3.73	1.10	6	High
11	The speech therapist used advanced supportive methods and technology appropriate for the type of my child's disorder.	3.73	1.13	7	High
7	A speech specialist will show me how to correct my child's speech disorders to do home training.	3.70	1.13	8	High
13	A speech therapist guided me on how to correct language disorders and how to mainstream the training that my child received into our family's activities and daily life.	3.58	1.16	9	High
10	Various appropriate tools and equipment, and teaching aids are available for the speech room.	3.56	1.15	10	High
15	A speech therapist gives me regular written reports on my child's condition and progress.	3.55	1.20	11	High
16	I notice the improvement of my child's performance level since he joined the speech sessions.	3.55	1.24	12	High
6	I was provided with a home follow-up record of the child that records each session's procedures to follow up on my child at home.	3.54	1.23	13	High
12	The speech specialist coordinates with the class teacher to set goals and follow up on generalizing training in activities of the classroom environment.	3.44	1.10	14	High
1	Taking into account setting a flexible schedule of sessions and that the number and time of sessions are appropriate for my child's condition.	3.44	1.11	15	High
5	I was provided with a copy of my child's plan containing the goals and the suggested timeframe for achieving them.	3.40	1.12	16	High
Speech and language training services		3.64	0.93		High

It is evident from Table (6) that the level of parents' satisfaction with the services of speech and language training provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina was high, with an arithmetic average of (3.64). It is also noticed that the value of the standard deviation of the general mean is equal to (0.93), and the arithmetic averages ranged between (3.40-3.88). Where came paragraph (9), which states: "My baby care staff is speaking to me in easy-to-understand language." In the first place, with an

arithmetic average of (3.88). This phrase can be explained in the first order, from parents' satisfaction to their feeling of respect for service providers because of their educational and cultural backgrounds, while paragraph (5), which states, "I have been provided with a copy of my child's plan that contains the goals and the suggested time frame to achieve them." Ranked last, with an arithmetic average of (3.40); and this result can be explained by the fact that some parents do not know their rights to follow up and see the progress of the individual educational program, and the lack of awareness of some specialists about the necessity of involving the family in all services provided to the child in its holistic sense, and not only limiting it to the initial stages of evaluation, and they consider that family participation is not productive, consequently, their failure to perform their duties towards the parent to provide him with a copy of the individual educational plan for their child to follow the course of the program, although this was mentioned in the organizational guide (2017) that one of the duties of the institution for the parent is to enable him to see everything related to his son's program, and involving the family in preparing programs and observing the progress of the child's program and the final evaluation to see the extent to which the goals are achieved.

The third dimension: educational support services

Table 7: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of parents' satisfaction with the educational support services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, arranged in descending order

N	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Level of satisfaction
6	The building is equipped for my child's use in terms of lighting, ventilation, security, and safety.	3.84	1.08	1	High
7	The times for providing support services at the organization are appropriate for my child and me.	3.78	1.09	2	High
9	The educational environment provides opportunities for social interaction with the peers around the child.	3.74	1.04	3	High
8	The institution environment is a stimulating environment rich in educational stimuli.	3.72	1.07	4	High
13	The institution has a security staff such as the guard, the incubator, and the reception staff.	3.66	1.19	5	High
5	The caregiver gives me clear information about all the support services my child will need.	3.65	1.08	6	High
14	The rest of the organization's staff, such as the guard, the incubator, and the reception staff, are good at dealing with my child.	3.63	1.18	7	High
1	My child is offered programs to modify unwanted behavior.	3.61	1.08	8	High
11	The institution provides transportation for my child in case he needs it.	3.56	1.20	9	High
4	The institution has the necessary classroom facilities to achieve the programs and services provided to people with disabilities.	3.55	1.08	10	High
3	The foundation allows me to meet with parents of other children to receive mutual support.	3.50	1.15	11	High
10	The child's program includes their participation in community activities.	3.43	1.11	12	High
12	There is cooperation between the foundation and other private, governmental, social, medical, and educational sectors.	3.38	1.13	13	Average
2	The foundation provides my children with extracurricular activities and trips to learn about the community's distinctive features.	3.14	1.16	14	Average
	Supportive educational services	3.58	0.86		High

Table (7) shows that the level of parents' satisfaction with the educational support services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina was high. With an arithmetic average of (3.58). It is also noted that the value of the standard deviation of the general average is equal to (0.86). The arithmetic averages ranged between (3.14-3.84). Where came paragraph (6), which states: "The building is equipped for my child's use in terms of lighting, ventilation, security, and safety." In the first place, with a mean of (3.84) and a high degree of satisfaction. This result can be explained by the fact that institutions attach special importance

to these aspects, and this is because she is aware that she deals with children with disabilities, who show many behavioral problems, and most of them may have a decrease in mental abilities, which contributes to their low awareness of the concept of danger. Also, private institutions and centers in Saudi Arabia are subject to supervision by the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Social Development, and conditions have been set concerning the centers' physical environment. While paragraph (2), which states: "The institution provides my child with extracurricular activities and trips to identify the distinctive features of society," ranked last with an arithmetic mean of (3.14) and a moderate degree of satisfaction. This may be due to the nature of what is imposed by the children's need of enriching their training or curricula and the need for them to live with more educational experiences outside the normal classroom environment. In light of the poor provision of such services, this would make parents agree on their dissatisfaction with the level of providing these services to their children.

The fourth dimension: family support services

Table 8: Arithmetic averages and deviations for parents' satisfaction with the family support services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, arranged in descending order

N	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Rank	Level of satisfaction
11	The foundation communicates with the families through correspondence, phone calls, and meetings.	3.88	1.06	1	High
3	In the institution, a family services plan is prepared to help the family deal with their child.	3.73	1.11	2	High
12	A speech therapist understands the difficulties family life imposes on my time and the effort I put into my child's programs.	3.56	1.10	3	High
5	A speech therapist provides rehabilitative guidance about the type of disorder my child has.	3.54	1.14	4	High
2	The foundation provides counseling and group therapy for families.	3.53	1.11	5	High
7	The foundation provides me with the special needs of my child and the options available for serving him.	3.45	1.12	6	High
4	The speech therapist holds regular meetings with the family to review my child's individualized treatment program.	3.43	1.15	7	High
10	The educational program team helps me improve my child's skills through courses, workshops, lectures, books, video recordings, and more.	3.42	1.22	8	High
9	The foundation provides families with educational brochures about speech and language disorders and methods of treating them.	3.40	1.15	9	High
6	I am introduced to my rights as a parent and my child's rights, such as facilities and material aid.	3.37	1.20	10	Average
1	The foundation refers me to the competent authorities to receive services that are not available to it.	3.36	1.14	11	Average
8	I am introduced to all institutions, services, and programs that can help my child and family.	3.31	1.20	12	Average
	Family support services	3.50	0.96		High

It is evident from Table (8) that the level of parents' satisfaction with the family support services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina was high, with an arithmetic average of (3.50). It is also noticed that the value of the standard deviation of the general average is equal to (0.96). Thus, family support services are at the top of the list of services with the least parents' satisfaction. The low level of satisfaction with these services can be explained by the inadequacy of institutions and special education programs in educating parents about their rights and the rights of their children by them as an educational agency. By other bodies concerned with providing health and social services and support, because of its importance in reducing the burden on parents and helping them perform their roles towards their children, despite the obligation of the "Individuals with Disabilities" Act since 1990 to protect the rights of the child and his parents, there is still a gap between best practices in early childhood special education and the concrete reality in the field. This evaluation shows the lack of concern of service providers in parents' rights and the lack

of awareness of parents of their rights and claims it in return. And the arithmetic averages in this dimension ranged between (3.31-3.88), where came paragraph (11), which states: "The Foundation communicates with the families through correspondence, phone calls, and meetings." In the first place, with a high degree of satisfaction, with an arithmetic average of (3.88). While paragraph (8), which states: "I am introduced to all institutions, services, and programs that can help my child and my family," ranked last, with an arithmetic average of (3.31) and a moderate degree of satisfaction.

Parents' low satisfaction with these services can be explained by their insufficient awareness of their rights and the rights of their children, and the optimal services that are supposed to be provided to support and guide the family, which may contribute to early diagnosis and treatment of their children or reduce their disorders.

The first sub-question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha 0.05 \geq$) to the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah due to the variables related to the parent (gender, age, educational level, monthly income)?

In order to answer this question, which examines the statistical differences according to the variables of the study, the answer was divided so that it dealt with each variable separately, as follows:

The differences are according to the type of parent variable

Table 9: Mean, standard deviations, and (T) test, for two independent samples to determine the differences between the responses of the sample members about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and lanToders in Medina according to the parent's gender variable

Axes	Gender	Number	Mean	Degree of freedom	"T" Value	Significance level
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Male	23	3.69	122	.288	.774
	Female	101	3.63			
Speech and language training services	Male	23	3.89	122	1.427	.156
	Female	101	3.58			
Supportive educational services	Male	23	3.80	122	1.305	.194
	Female	101	3.54			
Family support services	Male	23	3.62	122	.690	.492
	Female	101	3.47			
The total score of the questionnaire	Male	23	3.75	122	1.024	.308
	Female	101	3.56			

It is evident from Table (9) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah according to the parent gender variable, this indicates that the study sample members, despite their differences in gender (male/female), all agree in their assessment of the level of satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina. The results of the present study are consistent with the studies of Baothman (2016), Najem (2019), Al-Balawi (2019), Dougherty (2015), and (Slade et al., 2018). And they found that the parent gender variable did not affect the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children, the differences according to the parent's age variable.

Table 10: Calculating the arithmetic means and standard deviations and testing the One-Way Analysis to determine the significance of the differences between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah according to the parent's age

Axes	The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average of squares	(P) Value	Significance level
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Between groups	1.215	3	.405	.608	.611
	Within groups	79.865	120	.666		
	Total	81.080	123			
Supportive educational services	Between groups	4.909	3	1.636	1.955	.124
	Within groups	100.442	120	.837		
	Total	105.351	123			
Family support	Between	5.504	3	1.835	2.58	.057

services	groups						
The total score of the questionnaire	Within groups	85.225	120	.710			
	Total	90.728	123				
	Between groups	4.486	3	1.495	1.658	.180	
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Within groups	108.195	120	.902			
	Total	112.680	123				
	Between groups	3.046	3	1.015	1.558	.203	
Speech and language training services	Within groups	78.191	120	.652			
	Total	81.237	123				

It is evident from Table (10) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah according to the parent's age. This indicates that the study sample members, despite their age difference, all agree in assessing the level of satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina. This study's results are consistent with the findings of Bathman (2016) and Dougherty's (2015) study, which showed that there are no statistically significant differences in the degree of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children according to different age groups of parents. Nordstrom (2017) showed an inverse relationship between parents' age and their level of satisfaction with services, as younger parents were more satisfied and accepting than older parents as parents became more aware of their rights and aspirations as their child grew older.

The differences according to the educational level variable

Table 11: Calculating the arithmetic averages and standard deviations and testing the One-Way Analysis to determine the significance of the differences between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah according to the educational level

Axes	Source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average of squares	(P) Value	Significance level
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Between groups	1.225	3	.408	.614	.607
	Within groups	79.855	120	.665		
	Total	81.080	123			
Supportive educational services	Between groups	2.773	3	.924	1.081	.360
	Within groups	102.578	120	.855		
	Total	105.351	123			
Family support services	Between groups	7.750	3	2.583	3.736	*.013
	Within groups	82.978	120	.691		
	Total	90.728	123			
The total score of the questionnaire	Between groups	9.327	3	3.109	3.610	*.015
	Within groups	103.353	120	.861		
	Total	112.680	123			
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Between groups	4.317	3	1.439	2.245	.087
	Within groups	76.919	120	.641		
	Total	81.237	123			

Table (11) shows that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, according to the educational level in the

dimensions (diagnostic and evaluation services, speech and language training services, and at the level of the total score of the questionnaire). Where the values of the significance level reached (0,611), (0,360), and (0,087) respectively, which are values greater than the level of significance (0.05) and not statistically significant, while there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) in the dimensions (educational support services, Family Support Services); where the significance level values reached (0,013), (0,015) and to determine the direction of differences, the post/test (Scheffe) was used. Table (12) shows the direction of these differences.

Table 12: Scheffe test results for significant differences due to educational level variable

Axis	Experience (years)	Mean	secondary	Bachelor	Postgraduate
Supportive educational services	Average and lower	3.91	.209	.6133*	.373
	secondary	3.70	-	.40467	.16482
	Bachelor	3.30	-.40467	-	-.23985
	Postgraduate	3.54	-.16482	.23985	-
Family support services	Average and lower	3.85	0.1877	0.64113*	0.57674
	secondary	3.66	-	.45343	.38904
	Bachelor	3.21	-.45343	-	-.06439
	Postgraduate	3.27	-.38904	.06439	-

It is clear from Table (12) that:

- The existence of statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the educational level variable between the level (average or less) and the (bachelor) level in the dimension of (educational support services) and in favor of the level (medium or less).

- The existence of statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the educational level variable between the level (average or less) and the (bachelor) level in the dimension of (family support services) and in favor of the level (medium or less).

This indicates that the educational level variable impacted parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children. This can be explained by the fact that families with a higher educational level often look for information that increases their awareness of the situation of their children and thus participate in making appropriate decisions for their children and learn about the services provided and the extent to which the child benefits from them, this is reflected in their acceptance and satisfaction of the services provided. Whereas families with a lower educational level are only interested in having additional services in the institution provided to their children regardless of the quality of these services. This result is consistent with the study of Baothman (2016) and Najm (2019), whose results showed an inverse relationship between parents' education level and their levels of satisfaction and acceptance; it was found that the less educated parents were more satisfied and accepting than the more educated parents. In contrast, the Nordstrom study (2017) showed that the satisfaction averages were slightly higher for parents with a college education versus those with a high school diploma. However, this result is not in agreement with Al-Balawi (2019) results and (Slade et al., 2018), which did not show differences attributed to the parents' educational level.

Differences according to the variable of monthly income

Table 13: Means and standard deviations and testing the One-Way Analysis to determine the significance of the differences between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina according to the monthly income variable

Axes	The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average of squares	(P) Value	Significance level
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Between groups	.309	2	.155	.232	.793
	Within groups	80.770	121	.668		
	Total	81.080	123			
Speech and language training services	Between groups	.659	2	.330	.381	.684
	Within groups	104.691	121	.865		
	Total	105.351	123			
Supportive educational services	Between groups	1.405	2	.702	.952	.389
	Within groups	89.323	121	.738		
	Total	90.728	123			
Family support	Between	2.584	2	1.292	1.420	.246

services	groups					
	Within groups	110.096	121	.910		
	Total	112.680	123			
The total score of the questionnaire	Between groups	1.033	2	.516	.779	.461
	Within groups	80.204	121	.663		
	Total	81.237	123			

Table (13) shows no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the responses of the study sample individuals, the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, according to the monthly income. Where the significance level values reached (0,793), (0,684), (0,389), (0,246), (0,461), respectively. These values are greater than the significance level (0.05) and are not statistically significant. This indicates that the study sample members, despite their monthly income difference, but all agree in their assessment of the level of satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina. The results of the current study are in agreement with the studies of Bathman (2016), Al-Najem (2019), and Al-Balawi (2019), which indicated that there was no relationship between the family's monthly income and their satisfaction with the services provided to their children.

The second sub-question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah due to the variables about the child (gender, age, type of institution, and the duration of the child's enrollment in the institution)?

To answer this question, which examines the statistical differences according to the study variables, the answer was divided as it dealt with each variable separately, as follows:

Differences according to the variable of the child's gender

Table 14: Means, standard deviations, and (T) test, for two independent samples to determine the differences between the responses of the sample members about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina according to the child's gender variable

Axes	The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average of squares	(P) Value	Significance level
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Male	50	3.60	122	-.447	.655
	Female	74	3.67			
Speech and language training services	Male	50	3.66	122	.174	.862
	Female	74	3.63			
Supportive educational services	Male	50	3.43	122	-1.629	.106
	Female	74	3.69			
Family support services	Male	50	3.31	122	-1.854	.066
	Female	74	3.63			
The total score of the questionnaire	Male	50	3.50	122	-1.031	.305
	Female	74	3.65			

It is evident from Table (14) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the responses of the study sample individuals to the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina according to the child's gender variable, where the significance level reached (0.655, 0.862, 0.106, 0.066, 0.305), respectively. It is greater than (0.05) and not statistically significant, indicating that the study sample individuals despite their difference in the gender of the child (male/female) however, they all agree in their appreciation of the level of satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina. This indicates that the child's gender variable had no effect on parents' satisfaction, and this indicates that the services these children receive are similar regardless of whether they are male or female. This result is consistent with Baothman (2016) and (Slade et al., 2018). Due to the increased awareness of specialists and their belief that services remain the most important from their point of view, whether the child is male or female.

Differences according to the child's age variable.

Table 15: Means and standard deviations and a One-Way Analysis test, to determine the significance of the differences between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah according to age

Axes	The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average of squares	(P) Value	Significance level
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Between groups	11.558	3	3.853	6.650	.000
	Within groups	69.522	120	.579		
	Total	81.080	123			
Speech and language training services	Between groups	12.457	3	4.152	5.364	.002
	Within groups	92.894	120	.774		
	Total	105.351	123			
Supportive educational services	Between groups	16.047	3	5.349	8.595	.000
	Within groups	74.682	120	.622		
	Total	90.728	123			
Family support services	Between groups	17.328	3	5.776	7.269	.000
	Within groups	95.352	120	.795		
	Total	112.680	123			
The total score of the questionnaire	Between groups	12.580	3	4.193	7.329	.000
	Within groups	68.656	120	.572		
	Total	81.237	123			

Table (15) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the study sample individuals' responses about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Medina, according to the child's age. To determine the direction of differences, the posttest (Scheffe) was used. Table (16) shows the direction of these differences.

Table 16: Scheffe test results for significant differences that are attributed to the child's age variable

Axis	Experience (years)	Arithmetic average	From 6 to 9	From 9 to 12	More than 12
Diagnostic and evaluation services	Less than 6	4.00	.40503	.93810*	.22389
	From 6 to 9	3.59	-	.53307	-.18113
	From 9 to 12	3.06	-	-	-.71420-*
	More than 12	3.77	-	-	-
Speech and language training services	Less than 6	4.09	.56220	.96845*	.36774
	From 6 to 9	3.53	-	.40625	-.19446
	From 9 to 12	3.12	-	-	-.60071
	More than 12	3.72	-	-	-
Supportive educational services	Less than 6	3.79	.46259	.67687*	-.28111
	From 6 to 9	3.32	-	.21429	-.74369-*
	From 9 to 12	3.11	-	-	-.95798*
	More than 12	4.07	-	-	-
Family support services	Less than 6	3.70	.41905	.77817*	-.27841
	From 6 to 9	3.28	-	.35913	.35913
	From 9 to 12	2.92	-	-	-1.05658-*
	More than 12	3.98	-	-	-
The total score of the questionnaire	Less than 6	3.89	.46222	.84040*	.00803
	From 6 to 9	3.43	-	.37818	-.45418
	From 9 to 12	3.05	-	-	-.83237*
	More than 12	3.89	-	-	-

It is clear from Table No. (16) that:

- There were statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the responses of the study sample individuals about the level of parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders in Madinah according to the child's age between age (less than 6) and age (from 9 to 12) (in All dimensions, at the level of the total score of the questionnaire) and in favor of age (less than 6).

- Likewise, there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the child's age variable between age (from 9 to 12) and age (more than 12) in the dimension (diagnostic

and evaluation services, educational support services, family support services) and in favor of age (More than 12).

- There are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the variable of the child's age between age (from 6 to 9) and age (more than 12) in the dimension of (supportive educational services) and favor of age (more than 12).

- There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the child age variable between age (less than 6) and age (from 9 to 12) in (the total score of the questionnaire) and in favor of age (less than 6). There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the child's age variable between age (from 9 to 12) and age (more than 12) in favor of age (more than 12).

- There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the child age variable between age (less than 6) and age (from 9 to 12) in (the total score of the questionnaire) and in favor of age (less than 6). There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the child's age variable between age (from 9 to 12) and age (more than 12) in favor of age (more than 12).

As we note, the parents' consent came once in favor of younger children and once in favor of older children, and the researcher explains this difference according to the age variable, given the different nature of services and service delivery models across different age groups. The results of the current study support the findings of the study (Templeman, 2019), which showed that there is a relationship between the child's age and the level of parental satisfaction. And she emphasized that the greater the child's age, the greater the parents' satisfaction and desire to relate to the program and the services provided. Whereas, the results of the current study differ from the study of Baothman (2016), Nordstrom (2017), and (Slade et al., 2018), which showed no correlation between parental satisfaction and child age.

Recommendations

- Informing parents of their rights and their children's rights with speech and language disorders guaranteed by regulations a

- study's finding standardized tests for the diagnosis of speech and language disorders, which are applied uniformly in all institutions.

- Providing an official form that measures parents' satisfaction with the services provided to their children with speech and language disorders. This measure is taken into account when undertaking the process of reviewing, amending, and developing services by decision-makers and officials.

- Holding awareness workshops for parents or events to present and discuss ideas and problems.

- Work to improve the quality of services provided to children with speech and language disorders, leading to satisfaction.

- Increasing the interest of specialists and workers in institutions in the importance of working with parents and providing them with the necessary skills to build partnerships with families in line with achieving the expected vision (2030).

- Conducting a study considering the expansion of the sample to include parents of children with speech and language disorders in all regions of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

- Conducting further studies in the study population to consider other variables that may impact the satisfaction of parents of children with speech and language disorders.

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